

SAHANA :CHAT APPLICATION INCLUSIVE AND ACCESSIBLE TO ALL

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Abstract- Sahana is an innovative, accessible, and inclusive chat application designed to bridge the communication gap for visually impaired, deaf, and non-speaking individuals. Traditional digital communication platforms often overlook the unique needs of these communities, resulting in significant barriers to participation, engagement, and social interaction. These challenges arise from a lack of adequate accessibility features, making it difficult for individuals with disabilities to communicate effectively and independently. Recognizing these limitations, Sahana has been developed as a comprehensive solution that leverages advanced accessibility technologies to ensure seamless and inclusive communication for all users

I.INTRODUCTION

In today's interconnected world, digital communication platforms play a vital role in connecting people, yet they often present significant challenges for individuals with visual impairments, hearing impairments, or speech disabilities. Traditional platforms frequently lack essential accessibility features, making it difficult for such users to engage in conversations, access information, or participate fully in social and professional interactions. Recognizing these barriers, Sahana emerges as an innovative chat application designed to provide a fully accessible and inclusive communication experience for visually impaired, deaf, and non-speaking individuals. By integrating advanced accessibility technologies, Sahana ensures that all users, regardless of their abilities, can communicate effortlessly and independently in real-time. The platform incorporates Text-to-Speech (TTS) functionality to assist visually impaired users by converting text-based messages into audible speech, enabling them to follow conversations with ease. Simultaneously, Speech-to-Text (STT) technology allows non-speaking and hearing-impaired users to convert spoken words into text, facilitating

clear and accurate communication. Additionally, Sahana features emoji voice-over, which provides audio descriptions of emojis to ensure visually impaired users can fully understand the emotional tone and context of messages. To further enhance usability, Sahana offers intuitive gesture-based controls, allowing users to perform key actions such as sending messages or navigating menus through simple hand movements. Voice-guided navigation supports visually impaired users by providing step-by-step audio instructions, while tactile feedback offers vibration cues to confirm successful interactions. Built using the Django framework with an ASGI server (Daphne) and Web-Sockets for real-time messaging, Sahana ensures fast, responsive communication with minimal delays, even in dynamic environments. By combining these powerful features, Sahana effectively eliminates communication barriers, empowering individuals with disabilities to participate actively in digital conversations, connect with others, and access information with greater ease and independence.

II.LITERATURE SURVEY

The literature survey highlights various advancements in multilingual communication, accessibility, and sentiment analysis. Key studies emphasize the effectiveness of multilingual language models for improved sentiment analysis accuracy, demonstrating the potential of cross-linguistic data in enhancing classification outcomes. Research on Google Cloud APIs showcases successful multilingual speech recognition and translation systems, improving accessibility for diverse users. Transformer-based models like mT5 have proven efficient in translating

Indian languages, while voice-enabled systems offer hands-free access to digital content for visually impaired users. Studies exploring code-switching techniques reveal enhanced translation quality through lexico-semantic enrichment, while voice-based form-filling systems simplify data entry for visually challenged individuals. Furthermore, research on gesture-based controls, motion recognition, and voice command activation highlights innovative methods to assist physically disabled users in interacting with devices. Sentiment analysis research integrating emoji-based features and WhatsApp message preprocessing offers improved emotion detection in social networking contexts. Lastly, studies on abstractive text summarization demonstrate enhanced readability and coherence in presenting large volumes of online data. Collectively, these advancements offer valuable insights for developing inclusive platforms like Sahana, ensuring seamless communication and accessibility for individuals with disabilities.

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Individuals with visual impairments, hearing impairments, and speech disabilities face numerous challenges in accessing and participating in digital communication platforms. For visually impaired users, navigating complex user interfaces, reading text messages without effective screen reader support, and interpreting multimedia content lacking descriptive alt text can be daunting. Deaf and hard-of-hearing individuals often struggle with missed audio alerts, limited access to real-time transcription services, and an absence of visual cues, making it difficult to engage in spontaneous conversations or follow audio-based content. Non-speaking individuals face communication barriers as they rely heavily on text-to-speech systems or alternative communication devices, which are not always integrated seamlessly into mainstream platforms. Current assistive

technologies fail to comprehensively address these diverse challenges, emphasizing the need for a tailored communication platform that offers inclusive features, such as enhanced screen reader compatibility, real-time transcription, visual alerts, and robust text-to-speech capabilities. By developing an accessible solution that meets the unique needs of these communities, digital communication can become truly inclusive, empowering individuals with disabilities to connect, express themselves, and engage without barriers.

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

A. System Architecture

The system architecture for the Sahana chat application is designed to support an inclusive communication platform that caters to visually impaired, deaf, and non-speaking users. The architecture comprises multiple components that work seamlessly to ensure accessibility, real-time communication, and usability. The frontend interface serves as the user-facing component, providing an intuitive and accessible experience through web browsers and mobile applications. The interface is designed with accessibility features such as screen reader compatibility, voice prompts, and gesture-based controls to ensure that users can easily navigate and interact with the platform.

The backend server is the central processing unit of the Sahana application, built using the Django framework and deployed with an ASGI server (Daphne) to handle asynchronous communication. By leveraging Web-Sockets, the server ensures instant message delivery and real-time updates for all users. This architecture also integrates third-party APIs for advanced functionalities like text-to-speech (gTTS) and speech-to-text (Speech-Recognition), making communication seamless for users with different accessibility needs. The system employs Web-Sockets to ensure real-time

communication between the frontend and backend components. This enables immediate message delivery and updates, ensuring that users are constantly informed of new messages or events during chat sessions. The architecture is also designed to be scalable, ensuring that the system can handle increasing traffic and user interactions without sacrificing performance.

The DBMS stores user data, chat messages, and other application-related information in a structured and organized manner. PostgreSQL is used as the preferred database management system for its reliability, scalability, and support for complex data structures. The speech recognition module is responsible for converting spoken words from blind users into text format for processing and display. It utilizes speech recognition libraries such as Speech-Recognition to accurately transcribe spoken words into text. The text-to-speech module converts text messages and other textual content into synthesized speech output for blind users. It uses libraries such as g-TTS (Google Text-to-Speech) or other text-to-speech APIs to generate natural and expressive speech output.

B. System design flowchart

Fig 1 System Design Flowchart

IV IMPLEMENTATION

A. Pseudocode

Step 1-Authenticate user credentials and initialize the user session, ensuring secure access to the chat application

Step 2- Users compose and send messages, while the system processes and delivers incoming messages in real-time

Step 3- For visually impaired users, text messages are converted to speech using the text-to-speech module and played back.

Step 4- Capture spoken words from users and transcribe them into text using the speech-to-text module, ensuring bidirectional communication

Step 5- Enable real-time messaging using Web-Sockets, updating the interface dynamically as new messages are received or sent.

B. Important implementation tools and techniques

The Sahana project leverages the Django framework as its backend, utilizing Django ORM to manage interactions with the PostgreSQL database, which securely stores user data, chat history, accessibility settings, and multilingual content. To facilitate real-time messaging, the project employs the ASGI server (Daphne) alongside the WebSocket protocol, ensuring seamless and instant communication. Accessibility features include gTTS (Google Text-to-Speech) for converting text-based chat messages into speech and the Speech-Recognition library for transcribing spoken input into text, enabling inclusive interaction. Additionally, gesture-based and voice control integration enhances usability for individuals with disabilities. The project also incorporates an emoji picker to enrich user interaction, making communication more expressive and engaging. Furthermore, Django’s built-in security mechanisms protect against SQL injection, cross-site scripting (XSS), and other vulnerabilities, ensuring data integrity

and privacy. A responsive and adaptive user interface (UI) design ensures accessibility, providing an intuitive experience for all users.

V. RESULT ANALYSIS

Fig 2. Both user online

Fig 3. File or image sent

Fig 4. Blind user interface

Fig 5.Emoji Picker

VI CONCLUSION

Sahana is more than just a chat application—it's a step toward truly inclusive communication. By integrating accessibility at its core, we ensure that everyone, regardless of their abilities, can connect seamlessly. The application successfully bridges communication gaps by incorporating features like text-to-speech (TTS), speech-to-text (STT), gesture-based controls, and multilingual support, making conversations more accessible and expressive.

However, like any evolving project, Sahana has areas that can be improved. The UI/UX of the login page could be enhanced to provide a more intuitive and visually appealing experience. Additionally, while users can share documents and files, these cannot be opened directly within the application due to security restrictions, requiring manual downloads instead. Future iterations of the project could focus on refining these aspects, improving performance, and integrating additional features like real-time sign language recognition and secure in-app file viewing.

Sahana is a significant step toward a more inclusive digital space, and with continued improvements, it has the potential to redefine accessible communication for all users.

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